

Original Article

Publication History:
Published 1/1/2021

DOI:
10.5281/zenodo.4432922

Corresponding Author:
Dr. Amjad Ali,
RHC Sherghar
amjadalisafi@gmail.com

Cite this article as:
Liaqat B, Ahmad O, Ali A.
Prevalence of motion
sickness among patients
presenting in outdoor
department. Int. J. Med.
Dent. Allied Health Sci.
2020;3(1). 776-79

© **Copyright 2020**
This is an open access article
distributed under the terms of the
Creative Commons Attribution
License CC-BY 4.0., which
permits unrestricted use,
distribution, and reproduction in
any medium, provided the
original author and source are
credited.

**PREVALENCE OF MOTION SICKNESS
AMONG PATIENTS PRESENTING IN
OUTDOOR DEPARTMENT**

AUTHORS:

1. DR. BUSHRA LIAQAT, RAWALPINDI MEDICAL UNIVERSITY
2. DR OWAIS AHMAD, TEACHING HOSPITAL DGKHAN
3. DR. AMJAD ALI, RHC SHERGHAR

ABSTRACT:

Motion sickness occurs due to a difference between actual and expected motion. Symptoms commonly include nausea, vomiting, cold sweat, headache, sleepiness, yawning, loss of appetite, and increased salivation. Complications may rarely include dehydration, electrolyte problems, or a lower esophageal tear. This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender and history of motion sickness were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. A total of 60 patients presenting in outdoor department were included in this study i.e., 30 males (50%) and 30 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 26.13 ± 3.11 years. Out of these patients, five patients presented with history of motion sickness.

Keyword: Motion Sickness

INTRODUCTION:

Motion sickness occurs due to a difference between actual and expected motion. Symptoms commonly include nausea, vomiting, cold sweat, headache, sleepiness, yawning, loss of appetite, and increased salivation. Complications may rarely include dehydration, electrolyte problems, or a lower esophageal tear. The cause of motion sickness is either real or perceived motion. This may include from car travel, air travel, sea travel, space travel, or reality simulation. Risk factors include pregnancy, migraines, and Meniere's disease. The diagnosis is based on symptoms.

Treatment may include behavioral measures or medications. Behavioral measures include keeping the head still and focusing on the horizon. Three types of medications are useful: antimuscarinics such as scopolamine, H1 antihistamines such as dimenhydrinate, and amphetamines such as dexamphetamine. Side effects, however, may limit the use of medications. A number of medications used for nausea such as ondansetron are not effective for motion sickness. Nearly all people are affected with sufficient motion. Susceptibility, however, is variable. Women are more easily affected than men. Motion sickness has been described since at least the time of Hippocrates. "Nausea" is from the Greek naus meaning ship. Symptoms commonly include nausea, vomiting, cold sweat, headache, sleepiness, yawning, loss of appetite, and increased salivation. Occasionally tiredness can last for hours to days an episode of motion sickness, known as "sopite syndrome". Rarely severe symptoms such as the inability to walk, ongoing vomiting, or social isolation may occur (1-3).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender and history of motion sickness were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were

presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

A total of 60 patients presenting in outdoor department were included in this study i.e., 30 males (50%) and 30 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 26.13 ± 3.11 years. Out of these patients, five patients presented with history of motion sickness.

DISCUSSION:

Roughly one-third of people are highly susceptible to motion sickness, and most of the rest get motion sick under extreme conditions. The rates of space motion sickness have been estimated at between forty and eighty percent of those who enter weightless orbit. Several factors influence susceptibility to motion sickness, including sleep deprivation and the cubic footage allocated to each space traveler. Studies indicate that women are more likely to be affected than men, and that the risk decreases with advancing age. There is some evidence that people with Asian ancestry may develop motion sickness more frequently than people of European ancestry, and there are situational and behavioral factors, such as whether a passenger has a view of the road ahead, and diet and eating behaviors. Three types of medications are useful: antimuscarinics such as scopolamine, H1 antihistamines such as dimenhydrinate, and amphetamines such as dexamphetamine.

Benefits are greater if used before the onset of symptoms or shortly after symptoms begin. Side effects, however, may limit the use of medications. Several medications used for nausea such as ondansetron and metoclopramide are not effective in motion sickness. Scopolamine is the most effective medication. Evidence is best for when it is used preventatively. It is available as a skin patch. Side effects may include blurry vision. Other effective first-generation antihistamines include meclizine, promethazine, cyclizine, and cinnarizine. In pregnancy meclizine and dimenhydrinate are

generally felt to be safe. Side effects include sleepiness. Second generation antihistamines have not been found to be useful. Dextroamphetamine may be used together with an antihistamine or an antimuscarinic. Concerns include their addictive potential. Those involved in high-risk activities, such as SCUBA diving, should evaluate the risks versus the benefits of medications. Promethazine combined with ephedrine to counteract the sedation is known as "the Coast Guard cocktail" (4-6).

REFERENCES:

1. Bitterman N, Eilender E, Melamed Y (May 1991). "Hyperbaric oxygen and scopolamine". *Undersea Biomedical Research*. 18 (3): 167–74. PMID 1853467. Archived from the original on 2008-08-20. Retrieved 2008-05-09.
2. Williams TH, Wilkinson AR, Davis FM, Frampton CM (March 1988). "Effects of transcutaneous scopolamine and depth on diver performance". *Undersea Biomedical Research*. 15 (2): 89–98. PMID 3363755. Retrieved 2008-05-09.
3. Arieli R, Shupak A, Shachal B, Shenedrey A, Ertracht O, Rashkovan G (1999). "Effect of the anti-motion-sickness medication cinnarizine on central nervous system oxygen toxicity". *Undersea and Hyperbaric Medicine*. 26 (2): 105–09. PMID 10372430. Retrieved 2008-05-09.
4. East Carolina University Department of Diving & Water Safety. "Seasickness: Information and Treatment" (PDF).
5. Brainard A, Gresham C (2014). "Prevention and treatment of motion sickness". *Am Fam Physician*. 90 (1): 41–46. PMID 25077501.
6. Hromatka BS, Tung JY, Kiefer AK, Do CB, Hinds DA, Eriksson N (May 2015). "Genetic variants associated with motion sickness point to roles for inner ear development, neurological processes and glucose homeostasis". *Hum. Mol. Genet*. 24 (9): 2700–08. doi:10.1093/hmg/ddv028. PMC 4383869. PMID 25628336.